

IEEE WFCS: A Historical Perspective

The history of the IEEE International Conference on Factory Communication Systems (WFCS), from its first edition in 1995 onward*

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The IEEE International Conference on Factory Communication Systems (WFCS) is the only IEEE conference dedicated specifically to communication for industrial automation systems.

On October 4, 1995, the adventure began. The first edition of WFCS was a workshop, the 1st IEEE International Workshop on Factory Communication Systems (WFCS), and it was organized in the small village of Leysin in the Vaud Alps, Switzerland. It was a rather small and restricted event, like all the subsequent editions of WFCS, where 29 full regular papers were presented. On those days, proceedings were printed. In Fig. 1, the photos of the proceedings of the first three editions of WFCS are reported. The last layout was used until the WFCS 2012 edition, where it was the last time the proceedings were printed. Since then, only the digital format has been made available.

Already from the very beginning, the main research topic of WFCS was communication for industrial automation systems, and in the paper titles, you can see evergreen keywords as “redundancy”, “vehicle bus”, “real-time”, “fault-tolerance”, “formal specification/modeling”, and “wireless LANs”.

*This work builds upon “30 years of WFCS: from 1995 in Leysin onward” by Frank Golasowski and Stefano Scanzio, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 License (CC BY-SA 4.0). The original work is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15839247> [1]. The present work includes modifications and additional contributions. This work is distributed under the same CC BY-SA 4.0 license.

Figure 1: Proceedings of the first three editions of WFCS.

WFCS was a biannual conference, but the event scheduled in 1999 for Magdeburg (Germany) was skipped, and the conference returned to a biannual periodicity, starting from its 2000 edition in Porto. In that year, submissions were managed by email; however, if this was not possible, authors had the option to send five printed copies. Work-in-Progress (WiP) papers are listed among the possible types of submission, but they were not included in the proceedings of the conference (i.e., they were only published on the conference webpage). In WFCS 2000, the early registration for non-IEEE members was 87500 Portuguese Escudo (PTE), which corresponds to 436.45 euros. Applying the inflation of the last 25 years, the re-evaluated early registration fee is 750 euros.

Starting from WFCS 2004, WiP papers were included in the proceedings and published in the IEEE Xplore catalog, and the industry day was first included in the conference program.

In the 2006 edition, the program committee participants met in person three months prior to the conference to select papers. After the introduction of conference management systems such as the IES Conferences Community, the software platform takes care of the coordination of the review process.

In 2015, WFCS became an annual event, and its name was changed to IEEE World Conference on Factory Communication Systems, to reflect its characteristics closer to a conference than a workshop. This was valid until 2017, when the name was restored to IEEE International

Figure 2: Some logos of past editions of WFCS.

Workshop on Factory Communication Systems.

This was only a parenthesis, however, because starting from the 2020 edition, WFCS was definitely identified as a conference with the current name IEEE International Conference on Factory Communication Systems. Starting from that year, the IEEE IES Technical Committee on Factory Automation (TCFA) has been a co-sponsor of the event.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the three editions WFCS 2020, WFCS 2021, and WFCS 2022 were carried out completely online.

Finally, the last 2025 edition of WFCS introduces tutorials and demonstrations, and it becomes a four-day event. The WFCS 2025 conference is the first IEEE conference to be held in the city of Rostock.

The logos of WFCS are all characterized by the name of the conference, the year, and the skyline of the hosting city. Fig. 2 reports some logos that can still be found on the internet from past editions.

Table 1 reports the location, dates, general chairs, program chairs, and number of submitted papers of all the editions of WFCS. Typically, WFCS takes place during the spring, with a preference for April and May, although some editions have also been held in June, August, September, or October. The conference with the highest number of published papers was WFCS 2008, with 37 regular and 20 WiP contributions. All editions are characterized by two

Table 1: Chronostory of all the editions of WFCS. The first number in the “Papers” column refers to regular papers, while the second number refers to Work-in-Progress papers.

Edition	Location	Date	General Chairs	Program Chairs	Papers
WFCS 1995	Leysin, Switzerland	4-6 October 1995	Josep M. Fuertes Richard Zurawski	Guy Juanole Alfred C. Weaver	29
WFCS 1997	Barcelona, Spain	1-3 October 1997	Josep M. Fuertes Richard Zurawski	Guy Juanole Alfred C. Weaver	44
WFCS 2000	Porto, Portugal	6-8 September 2000	Eduardo Tovar Richard Zurawski	Francisco Vasques Guy Juanole	40
WFCS 2002	Vasteras, Sweden	28-30 August 2002	Christer Norström Richard Zurawski	Hans A. Hansson	29
WFCS 2004	Vienna, Austria	22-24 September 2004	Dietmar Dietrich Richard Zurawski	Thilo Sauter Francisco Vasques	32+24
WFCS 2006	Turin, Italy	28-30 June 2006	Adriano Valenzano Josep M. Fuertes	Gianluca Cena Francisco Vasques	21+18
WFCS 2008	Dresden, Germany	21-23 May 2008	Martin Wollschlaeger Thilo Sauter	Gianluca Cena Françoise Simonot-Lion	37+20
WFCS 2010	Nancy, France	18-21 May 2010	Thilo Sauter Françoise Simonot-Lion	Julián Proenza Andreas Willig	21+20
WFCS 2012	Lemgo, Germany	21-24 May 2012	Jürgen Jasperneite Thilo Sauter	Thomas Nolte Andreas Willig	20+22
WFCS 2014	Toulouse, France	5-7 May 2014	Zoubir Mammeri Richard Zurawski	Roman Obermaisser Eduardo Tovar	25+8
WFCS 2015	Palma de Mallorca, Spain	27-29 May 2015	Julian Proenza Thilo Sauter	Paulo Pedreiras Stefano Vitturi	27+18
WFCS 2016	Aveiro, Portugal	3-6 May 2016	Paulo Pedreiras Thilo Sauter	Lucia Lo bello Moris Behnam	24+17
WFCS 2017	Trondheim, Norway	31 May - 2 June 2017	Stig Petersen Richard Zurawski	Luca Durante Luis Lino Ferreira	23+14
WFCS 2018	Imperia, Italy	13-15 June 2018	Luca Durante Roberto Oboe	Liliana Cucu-Grosjean Lucia Seno	28+23
WFCS 2019	Sundsvall, Sweden	27-29 May 2019	Mikael Gidlund Thilo Sauter	Emiliano Sisinni Gerhard P. Hancke	18+12
WFCS 2020	Porto, Portugal	27-29 April 2020	Luis Almeida Ramez Daoud	Ahlem Mifdaoui Frank Golatowski	20+12
WFCS 2021	Linz, Austria	9-11 June 2021	Hans-Peter Bernhard Zhibo Pang	Leander Hörmann Emiliano Sisinni	20+10
WFCS 2022	Pavia, Italy	27-29 April 2022	Tullio Facchinetti Lukasz Wisniewski	Svetlana Girs Marco Porta	24+12
WFCS 2023	Pavia, Italy	26-28 April 2023	Tullio Facchinetti Lukasz Wisniewski	Marco Porta Stefano Scanzio	27+10
WFCS 2024	Toulouse, France	17-19 April 2024	Ahlem Mifdaoui Luis Almeida	Frank Golatowski Stefano Scanzio	20+10
WFCS 2025	Rostock, Germany	10-13 June 2025	Frank Golatowski Stefano Scanzio	Mohammad Ashjaei Ramez Daoud	32+16 +5 (demos)
WFCS 2026	Offenburg, Germany	21-24 April 2026	Axel Sikora Stefano Scanzio	Tullio Facchinetti Henning Trsek	27+15 +8 (demos)
WFCS 2027	Bilbao, Spain	20-23 April 2027	Pablo Angueira Frank Golatowski	Stefano Scanzio Zenepe Satka	—

general chairs and two program chairs, except for WFCS 2002, which was characterized by only one program chair. The more active chairs of WFCS were Thilo Sauter, who was 6 times general chair and 1 time program chair, and Richard Zurawski, who was 7 times general chair. The country with the highest number of instances of WFCS is Italy, which hosted the conference four times. Data about the submitted papers for the 2026 edition is not currently available because the conference has not yet occurred.

Instead, Table 2 lists the five most cited papers in the history of WFCS. In particular, the most cited paper is “IoT agriculture system based on LoRaWAN” by Danco Davcev, Kosta Mitreski, Stefan Trajkovic, Viktor Nikolovski, Nikola Koteli, which was published in WFCS

Table 2: The five most cited papers in the history of WFCS. Citations and views are those reported in the IEEE Xplore catalog on April 15, 2026.

Pos.	Paper	Year	Cit.	Views
1	“IoT agriculture system based on LoRaWAN”, D. Davcev, K. Mitreski, S. Trajkovic, V. Nikolovski, N. Koteli [2]	2018	145	4873
2	“A comprehensive simulation study of slotted CSMA/CA for IEEE 802.15.4 wireless sensor networks”, A. Koubaa, M. Alves, E. Tovar [3]	2006	128	1429
3	“Flexray - A communication network for automotive control systems”, R. Makowitz, C. Temple [4]	2006	122	592
4	“Using LoRa for industrial wireless networks” M. Rizzi, P. Ferrari, A. Flammini, E. Sisinni, M. Gidlund [5]	2017	107	3194
5	“Security threats and issues in automation IoT” P. Varga, S. Plosz, G. Soos, C. Hegedus [6]	2017	94	2111

2018 and reached 127 citations and 4725 views. It is interesting to notice that the five most cited papers are located in different editions of WFCS (i.e., 2006, 2017, and 2018), and that all these papers are related to industrial communication technologies, which is the main topic of the conference (i.e., LoRa/LoRaWAN, IEEE 802.15.4/WSN, FlexRay). The only exception is the last paper, which is related to security aspects of automation in the Internet of Things.

Many thanks to Gianluca Cena, who attended 18 of the 21 editions of WFCS starting from 1995, and to Luis Almeida for their valuable help in finding information about WFCS. If you have any interesting information about WFCS, which was not included in this article, please write to stefano.scanzio@cnr.it.

Welcome to the next 23rd IEEE International Conference on Factory Communication Systems, which will be held in 2027, April 20-23 in Bilbao, Spain.

References

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